

TALES OF THE MENTORS: THE NARRATIVE OF SEASONED COOPERATING TEACHERS

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Tales of the Mentors: The Narrative of Seasoned Cooperating Teachers

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Abstract

The main objective of this qualitative study was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of seasoned cooperating teachers. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating fourteen seasoned cooperating teachers from one public schools in Davao region were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interview. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: encouraging both challenges and joy in sharing knowledge and experience; dealing with pedagogical challenges instructing on the formulation of lesson plan; handling behaviors atypical in the student-teachers dynamic; and providing support student-teachers in improving classroom management skills due to their lack of experience. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following coping strategies essential: balancing and managing time; practicing open communication and feedbacking; consulting with colleagues for advice; and processing student-teachers self-reflection for guidance. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: inspire passion and commitment to the teaching profession; encourage continuous learning and personal development in teaching; consistently uphold diligence in dedication in teaching; and be a role model. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, student-teachers and researchers.

Keywords: *experiences, seasoned cooperating teachers, thematic analysis, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

Before educators can effectively impart learning to students using appropriate methods and strategies, seasoned cooperating teachers step in. They serve as mentors and models for aspiring educators, acting as a crucial link between theoretical knowledge from teacher preparation programs and its practical implementation in classrooms. Despite their pivotal role, these experienced mentors often face obstacles such as constrained planning time, the challenge of ceding control, and communication issues with student teachers. Adapting to sharing the classroom after years of independent teaching can also pose difficulties. Furthermore, stress, heavy workloads, and potential gaps in classroom management skills might impact the student teaching experience, affecting both the student teacher and the cooperating teacher (Barry et al., 2021).

In Thailand, cooperating teachers frequently encounter obstacles arising from insufficient training and support provided by overseeing universities, resulting in challenges when supervising pre-service teachers. Communication breakdowns, especially evident during post-lesson conferences, impede the growth and development of student teachers. This communication barrier often stems from the reluctance of student teachers to openly discuss their challenges with cooperating teachers. Furthermore, within this context, some student teachers grapple with unrealistic expectations or a misunderstanding of the rigorous demands of teaching, leading to difficulties managing stress and impacting their effectiveness within the classroom setting (Faikhanta & Clarke, 2019).

In Cagayan, Philippines, some cooperating teachers inadvertently intervene excessively in the student teacher's classroom, inadvertently creating disruptions that hinder effective teaching and learning. This interference, whether through overbearing guidance or conflicting instructions, blur the lines of authority and disrupt the student teacher's ability to manage the classroom confidently. Additionally, within the educational system's framework, cooperating teachers face issues stemming from inadequate course materials, curriculum limitations, and resource scarcities. These challenges directly affect the cooperating teacher's ability to provide comprehensive support and guidance to student teachers, impeding their capacity to facilitate a successful teaching practice (Andres et al., 2021).

With those citations, it was proven that seasoned cooperating teachers faced multifaceted challenges as they engaged themselves in guiding student teachers. These obstacles significantly impacted their ability to effectively mentor and guide these aspiring educators, thereby influencing their capacity to facilitate successful teaching practices. Motivated by these findings, this phenomenological study sought to delve into the experiences of seasoned cooperating teachers, aiming to comprehend how they navigated and coped with these challenges. By illuminating their experiences, this study presented a crucial opportunity to acknowledge, value, and leverage their expertise more effectively. Ultimately, it aimed to contribute substantially to the ongoing enhancement of teacher preparation programs, thus elevating the quality of education for future generations.

In alignment with this study's focus on the perspective of cooperating teachers, numerous research endeavors centered around student teachers and practice teaching have been conducted. Notably, studies like Rupp & Becker's (2021) "Situational Fluctuations in Student Teachers' Self-Efficacy and its Relation to Perceived Teaching Experiences" and Ó Gallchóir et al.'s (2019) "My Cooperating Teacher and I: How Pre-Service Teachers Story Mentorship During School Placement" shed light on the experiences of student teachers during their practicum. However, the distinct emphasis of this study lay in exploring the viewpoint of cooperating teachers, an aspect surprisingly underrepresented in the existing literature. This research sought to fill this gap by placing a primary focus on understanding

the narratives and experiences of seasoned cooperating teachers, providing a valuable and previously unexplored perspective within the realm of teacher mentoring and guidance.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to explore the experiences and perspectives of seasoned cooperating teachers in mentoring pre-service teachers. This research seeks to investigate how these educators balance their own teaching responsibilities with the needs of their mentees. This study aims to understand the challenges and opportunities that cooperating teachers face, as well as the strategies they use to support their mentees.

Additionally, the purpose of the study was to gain a deeper understanding of the mentoring process from the perspective of seasoned cooperating teachers, to identify the factors that contribute to successful mentoring relationships and to develop recommendations for programs and supports to help cooperating teachers be more effective in their roles. The findings of the study were used to develop recommendations for improving the mentoring process and better preparing pre-service teachers for their careers. This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of seasoned cooperating teachers in mentoring pre-service teachers?
2. How do seasoned cooperating teachers cope with the challenges they encounter in mentoring pre-service teachers?
3. What are the insights that seasoned cooperating teachers can share in mentoring pre-service teachers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research approach. Data were collected through interviews with seasoned cooperating teachers. The interviews were semi-structured, meaning that the interviewer had a set of questions to ask, but the participants were free to respond in their own words. The interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed. The transcripts were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns.

The findings of this study were disseminated through a variety of channels, including academic publications, conference presentations, and online workshops. The findings of this study were expected to make a significant contribution to the field of teacher education. By understanding the experiences and perspectives of seasoned cooperating teachers, more effective programs and supports could be developed to help them be more effective in their roles. This would ultimately benefit pre-service teachers and help them become better teachers.

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically focusing on a phenomenological approach. It emphasized that qualitative research entails an inquiry that is specific to engaging with observers who are immersed in the reality of the world. It also highlighted that this approach signifies a comprehensive and intricate comprehension of the subject matter, achievable solely by direct communication with individuals, enabling them to share their narratives based on the expectations and literature review findings in the future (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

In this context, the qualitative study's primary objective was to emphasize and explore experiences, rather than attempting to measure variables through correlational or experimental techniques. The study's overarching goal was to provide individuals with the opportunity to express their experiences and ensure that these narratives were heard and acknowledged. This approach was deemed ideal for the research, as it aligned perfectly with the researcher's intent to capture the experiences of public elementary school where seasoned cooperating teachers were assigned.

Furthermore, a qualitative research method that was employed was phenomenology. Phenomenology, as a research method, centered on exploring pre-reflective human experiences and was grounded in specific philosophical and humanistic traditions. Accordingly, the term "phenomenology" denoted the direct examination and depiction of events as they were consciously experienced by the individuals undergoing them (Manen & Adams, 2010).

In this study, the use of the phenomenological approach was justified because it aligned with the emerging issues observed among the participants. This approach was well-suited for revealing their individual experiences, challenges, and perspectives. Additionally, it was an apt choice as it enabled a qualitative exploration of a specific phenomenon.

Participants

In this research, a qualitative-phenomenological research design was employed. Participant selection was done purposefully, ensuring that individuals from various factors were included. As a result, no eligible participants were excluded based on these demographic factors. Furthermore, all participants were treated equally in terms of their exposure to the potential risks and benefits associated with the study.

Moreover, in this phenomenological study, the participants were selected from the Municipality of Kapalong. Based on my inclusion criteria, the ideal participants needed to possess the following characteristics: (1) they must have been an elementary seasoned cooperating

teachers; (2) they must have had five years and more of teaching experience; and (3) they must have been currently employed in a public school located within the Municipality of Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Additionally, the participants needed to demonstrate a willingness to participate in the study's proceedings.

Also, there were a total of 14 participants. Fourteen participants participated in in-depth interviews. The participants that the researcher selected and identified were actively involved in this qualitative study. This number, of fourteen participants for the in-depth interviews, was sufficient to reach the saturation point, where themes were extracted (Mason 2010).

Procedure

In the data collection, the researcher prepared an interview guide. The data were gathered through in-depth interviews (IDI) with the research participants through purposeful random sampling.

These qualitative data collection methods had a primary objective: to furnish valuable information that facilitated a profound comprehension of the underlying processes influencing observed outcomes and enabled an evaluation of shifts in people's perspectives over time. In essence, they served as instruments for delving into the intricacies of human experiences and perceptions, shedding light on the nuances that shaped the research findings.

In preparation for my study, the researcher ensured a thorough review by my assigned research advisor to guarantee its quality and ethical compliance. This meticulous evaluation encompassed all aspects of the research, from its objectives and methodology to ethical considerations. Upon successfully meeting the required standards and addressing any concerns raised during the review, the researcher anticipated receiving the advisor's signal to proceed with the study, highlighting the commitment to conducting future high-quality and ethically responsible research.

Secondly, in the study, the data collection process commenced with the utilization of purposive sampling. This method involved the identification of participants through direct observation. The decision was made to involve 14 individuals in this research, as this was the recommended number for conducting qualitative, phenomenological inquiries. These participants expressed their voluntary involvement by signing a consent form, signifying their full awareness of the study's details and their willingness to participate, emphasizing their voluntary contribution of knowledge essential to the study.

Additionally, 14 participants underwent one-on-one in-depth interviews to delve deeply into their individual perspectives and experiences. These interviews employed a consistent set of standardized questions to ensure data consistency and comparability. This approach aimed to comprehensively explore each participant's unique narrative and gather rich insights, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the research topic.

Throughout the research process, the focus remained on individual perspectives and personal experiences, fostering an environment free from judgment. In this qualitative framework, there were no absolute "right" or "wrong" answers; rather, the aim was to capture the diverse range of viewpoints and experiences. This approach facilitated a holistic understanding of the subject matter and recognized the validity of each participant's unique perspective (Dörnyei, 2007).

Data Analysis

Data analysis was one of the most intricate and less extensively discussed phases in the qualitative project (Thorne, 2000). In this study, the researcher employed thematic analysis to scrutinize the data collected. Thematic analysis, as a systematic process, was integrated into the data analysis, enabling the connection of thematic frequencies with the overall content, which proved highly advantageous. This approach facilitated the identification of variables and elements that shaped the phenomenon observed by the participants, given that their interpretations offered valuable justifications for their behaviors, attitudes, and ideas. The analysis encompassed data reduction, data visualization, and data conclusions, all essential steps within thematic analysis that assisted in inferring and validating the gathered data (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Hatch, 2002; Creswell, 2003; Marks & Yardly, 2004).

The process of writing up field notes and transcriptions involved the selection, focus, simplification, abstraction, and transformation of emerging data, commonly referred to as data reduction. This approach enabled the researcher to effectively organize and condensed the extensive dataset, making it more manageable. Additionally, during data reduction, decisions were made regarding which aspects of the acquired data should be emphasized, minimized, or omitted entirely to shed light on the pertinent issues. To facilitate the integration, management, sorting, and categorization of the substantial qualitative data employed in this methodology, the researcher enlisted the support of a data analyst specialist (Creswell, 2013).

Ethical Considerations

The primary focus of this future study was on public elementary seasoned cooperating teachers. Consequently, the initial responsibility of the researcher was to prioritize their well-being and ensure their safety, maintaining their trust throughout the research process. Furthermore, the researcher upheld ethical standards of conduct, including principles related to respect for individuals, their rights, principles of justice, obtaining informed consent, and safeguarding confidentiality (Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for person embodied an ethical guideline that involved treating potential research participants with courtesy and regard,

acknowledging their right to independently decide whether to participate in a study. In accordance with this principle, the researcher provided participants with comprehensive information about the study, ensuring they had a clear understanding of its nature. This included obtaining informed consent, signifying that participants willingly agreed to partake in the research with a full awareness of its characteristics and potential consequences, both positive and negative. By upholding the respect for individual principle, the researcher maintained the ethical integrity of the study while honoring the autonomy and rights of the participants (Munhall, 2012).

Before conducting interviews, the researcher secured participants' consent and thoughtfully organized the interview timetable to avoid any clashes with their academic commitments or other responsibilities. This proactive approach aimed to minimize disruptions to the participants' schedules, reducing the likelihood of rescheduling or interview cancellations.

Throughout the study, the researcher cultivated and sustained a relationship characterized by respect and politeness with the participants. Prior to recording conversations, consent was sought, and participants were encouraged to ask questions at any point. Additionally, the utmost confidentiality was maintained during the in-depth interviews. By nurturing rapport and engaging with participants in a manner that was respectful and considerate, the research adhered to ethical standards.

Consent was an additional way to illustrate respect for the research participants. Its primary function was to inform all participants about the aims and purposes of the forthcoming research. Participants were given written consent forms for their endorsement, signifying their agreement to take part in the in-depth interviews. Naturally, they were also informed about the study's results and findings (Creswell, 2012).

In accordance with ethical principles, the researcher provided participants with permission and consent letters containing a comprehensive outline of the study, including its methods, design, and procedures. These documents aimed to enhance participants' understanding of the study's essence, enabling them to make well-informed decisions about their involvement. Participants who chose not to participate had the opportunity to withdraw their consent, with an assurance that their data would remain confidential. By adhering to these ethical guidelines, the researcher ensured the study was conducted in a responsible and considerate manner.

Beneficence required a commitment to minimizing potential risks to the participants involved in this research, placing their well-being above any potential benefits. Ensuring the confidentiality of interviewees was a vital step to prevent any risks to each participant. Ongoing protection of all participants was guaranteed, with strict measures implemented to secure all data files (Bricki & Green, 2007).

To adhere to the principle of beneficence, measures were implemented to ensure participants' responses and personal information remained anonymous and confidential. To mitigate potential risks, in-person interactions with participants were avoided, opting instead for secure online communication. These precautions were diligently enforced to protect the well-being and interests of the participants, reaffirming a commitment to ethical research practices.

Furthermore, the data collected in this research study were exclusively used for the purposes outlined in the study's objectives. However, the study's findings were also disseminated through various channels, including presentations within the institution, publication in academic forums or journals, and presentations at conferences, whether at local, national, or international levels. By sharing the study's results, the researcher aimed to contribute to the broader knowledge base within their field of study.

Confidentiality, within the context of this research, was of utmost importance. It involved safeguarding the data, results, findings, and, most importantly, the participants themselves. To uphold this principle, rigorous measures were implemented to ensure the complete anonymity of all participants, ensuring that their identities remained undisclosed and fully protected. Additionally, a comprehensive approach was adopted to handle all research materials, including audio recordings, encoded transcripts, notes, both digital and hard copies of data, and any other relevant documents. Crucially, these materials were promptly and securely eliminated once the data analysis phase was successfully concluded, adhering strictly to ethical guidelines (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect the identities of participants and adhere to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, a discreet coding system was employed to represent each individual's responses. This coding method involved careful handling of any information that might inadvertently disclose the participants' identities, such as names, genders, ethnic backgrounds, or specific details about their employment or location. These precautions prevented any compromise to their anonymity. By utilizing effective coding techniques and other security measures, the privacy of participants was rigorously maintained, ensuring full respect for their confidentiality.

Justice entailed a fair allocation of both the potential risks and rewards associated with the research. Acknowledging the significant contributions of all participants, who played a pivotal role in the research's accomplishment, was crucial. Therefore, it was essential to extend appreciation to each participant for their committed involvement (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006).

In this study, participants received compensation as a way to acknowledge and appreciate their valuable time and efforts devoted to the research. Thoughtful tokens were provided to express gratitude for their contributions. This compensation was not only a recognition of their involvement but also a means to potentially assist participants in addressing any challenges that may have arisen during the study, promoting a positive perception of their participation.

The purposive sampling approach employed in this study ensured that no eligible participants were excluded based on factors such as age, gender, socio-economic status, or ethnicity. All participants were equally exposed to both the potential risks and benefits associated

with the study. Providing tokens served as an expression of gratitude for their commitment, ensuring that the research was conducted ethically and fairly for all participants.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants in the study were the seasoned cooperating teachers who were teaching in Clementa F. Royo Elementary School. They were all public seasoned cooperating teachers who were mentoring pre-service teacher for five year and more. There were total of fourteen (14) seasoned cooperating teachers involved in the study: fourteen (14) females.

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face inside the campus of Clementa F. Royo Elementary School via audio recording. The researcher asked the participants if they wanted to be interviewed. The researcher got what she wanted and both the interviewer and interviewee were pleased with the result, resulting in a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required. The participants were given the choice to refuse to respond to any question they considered unbeneficial or in opposition to their wishes. To ensure confidentiality, the information or data collected during the interviews was treated with the utmost confidentiality. Only the researcher and the participants had access to this information, which was shared verbally but not included in the study due to its nature.

Table. Participants of the study

<i>In-depth interviews (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>
Mrs. Red	IDI-01	47	Female
Mrs. Home	IDI-02	45	Female
Mrs. Leader	IDI-03	50	Female
Mrs. Casual	IDI-04	29	Female
Mrs. Short hair	IDI-05	34	Female
Mrs. Eye glass	IDI-06	53	Female
Mrs. Chocolate	IDI-07	57	Female
Mrs. Happy	IDI-08	37	Female
Mrs. Vowel2	IDI-09	36	Female
Mrs. Fresh	IDI-10	40	Female
Mrs. Hairband	IDI-11	38	Female
Mrs. On time	IDI-12	37	Female
Mrs. Diligent	IDI-13	44	Female
Mrs. Last	IDI-14	43	Female

In order to adhere to the data collection process, the researcher used smartphones to record the participants' responses during the interview. Additionally, the researcher requested permission from all the participants to record the entire conversation during the interview, and they all politely agreed. All participants were accommodating and comprehended the request, except for one condition: that their identities remain anonymous in the study.

All participants in each case were given pseudonyms in order to protect the identities of all the participants. Pseudonyms were also given to each participant to protect their identity as well. For instance, Mrs. Red was named for the participant who dressed in red during the interview session, while Mrs. Home was named for the participant who was interviewed in her house. Mrs. Leader was named for the participant who is one of the master leaders in their school, and Mrs. Casual was named for the participant who wore casual attire during the interview session. Mrs. Short Hair was named for the participant who had short hair, and Mrs. Eyeglass was named for the participant who wore eyeglasses during the interview session.

Mrs. Chocolate was named for the participant who shared that chocolate is her favorite, while Mrs. Happy was named for the participant who always smiled and laughed during the interview session. Mrs. Vowel2 was named for the participant who only had two vowels in her last name, and Mrs. Fresh was named for the participant who looked fresh during the interview session. Mrs. Hairband was named for the participant who was wearing a hairband during the interview session, while Mrs. On Time was named for the participant who shared that she knows how to manage her time. Mrs. Diligent was named for the participant who shared that she is diligent in terms of her work, and Mrs. Last was named for the participant who was the last to be interviewed.

Categorization of Data

After the interview, recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The researcher initiated the analysis through the process of coding. Coding was the technique of arranging resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the set of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation. Data results were presented in the form of table. The data gathered was handed to the data analyst for analysis of data and emerging themes.

The data was categorized into central themes based on the research questions, and these themes were presented. Thorough discussions were conducted vividly describe the emerged themes from the study, while the core ideas of the participants'

responses were also included in the table alongside the major themes.

In order to add trustworthiness of the study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility and transferability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify its authenticity.

Regarding transferability, the researcher said right away that the results were not generally applicable since these views were solely based on the participants personal experiences in the school.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of seasoned cooperating teachers in mentoring pre-service teachers?

This question aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of seasoned cooperating teachers regarding to their mentoring pre-service teacher for almost 5years and more. It sought to uncover the challenges, successes, and the journey of these seasoned cooperating teachers as they navigate their 5 years and more in mentoring pre-service teacher. In the responses of the participants, there were four emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes were: encountering both challenges and joy in sharing knowledge and experience, dealing pedagogical challenges in instructing on the formulation of lesson plans, handling behaviors atypical in the student-teacher dynamic and providing support student teachers in improving classroom management skills due to their lack of experience.

Table 2. *Experiences of Seasoned Cooperating Teachers in Mentoring Student-Teacher*

<i>Emerging themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Facing both Difficulties and Rewards in Sharing Wisdom	<p>“Dealing with the different attitudes of students can be confusing, especially when they don't claim to be experts in handling children yet. Children have various attitudes, they are diverse. So, in my experience it is challenging but worthwhile because we are happy to impart knowledge to them. They can also use this experience when they become teachers themselves in the future. That's how it is” (IDI-09)</p> <p>“It is really a good experience, like a mix of emotions. There is tiredness, sometimes frustration, and challenges, but what prevails for me is the happiness from my experience. I am happy because I became a part of their learning journey.” (IDI-03)</p> <p>“My experience is fulfilling too. As a teacher, when I have student teachers come to me, I provide them with inputs, teach them what they should do, and you feel like you have helped. Especially when they arrive with little knowledge but leave having improved, particularly those who are open-minded. It makes them happy and proud of themselves, as well as me.” (IDI-13)</p> <p>“My experience as a cooperating teacher is valuable because it allows me to guide student teachers on what they should do to prepare for their service. It's like being a mentor to them, helping them understand what tasks are necessary to fulfill their role as teachers.” (IDI-12)</p>
Handling Teaching Challenges in Creating Lesson Plans	<p>“One specific challenge is checking the lesson plan. As a pre-service teacher, I am more concerned about lesson planning than grammar. The structured lesson planning is somewhat new to me, so I find it a bit challenging based on my experiences.” (IDI-04)</p> <p>“In my experience as a cooperating teacher, mentoring involves guiding on how to create a lesson plan and what resources to use. Sometimes, parts of their plans do not align with their objectives, which becomes a challenge as a mentor.” (IDI-12)</p> <p>“The most challenging aspect is lesson planning, even though you've learned it in seminars and trainings before entering the field. For us cooperating teachers, even after a long time, lesson planning remains the most challenging. Despite the trainings, some may say it is just a little bit different, ma'am, but it's really different when it's actual. Lesson planning is the number one challenge.” (IDI-14)</p> <p>“In my experience as a seasoned cooperating teacher and mentoring pre-service teachers, there are still student teachers who have not been introduced to lesson planning yet...my first student teacher whom I had to teach lesson planning; I instructed her, and when I checked, everything was completed. But when I repeated the instructions, she looked confused and said, "Ma'am, what was that again?" "Huh?"..."What!? I just finished instructing you, and I already checked everything," I said, repeating the instructions because she forgot.” (IDI-05)</p>
Handling Behaviors Atypical in the Student-Teacher Dynamic	<p>"(I encountered a student teacher who was stricter than me. Some are lazy; when they prepare a lesson, they might have instructional materials, but now they have become too relaxed. They just grab a book...It's like in the first cycle, they weren't prepared—quite lazy, right?" (IDI-05)</p> <p>"Close-mindedness, when someone insists on doing things their way, they seek out information, but they're disappointed if they don't hear or see it, as if they can't adapt to your suggestions." (IDI-13)</p> <p>"Lack of initiative, that is what I hate the most. Pre-service teachers lacking initiative; if I do not assign them a task, they will not do anything. That's a complete lack of initiative."(IDI-06)</p> <p>"Based on last school year, I will not mention names, but there was a student teacher under me who would sit in the front, engrossed in their cellphone, even when the students were being too loud. They would not care and would just wait for me to take charge of the classroom. It is like they didn't have any initiative." (IDI-09)</p>
Guiding Student-Teachers to Improve Classroom Management Skills Due to	<p>"Sometimes you need to raise your voice so they will hear you, you have to put command in your voice so the children believe you, that's really the number one challenge for me as a seasoned cooperating teacher, how to manage the behavior of the children so they will listen to you, I tell them to act as a teacher." (IDI-01)</p>

Inexperience

"That is the only thing they handle in classroom management, the children don't really trust the student teachers much, it's really a challenge for us, they're just like us, we can control the children, and they're still afraid of getting scolded because, of course, they're still soft-graded." (IDI-09)

"Children really vary, they can say you're too much or too loaded, they can say you're overreacting, when a student acts like this. So now, if you are not assertive in your classroom, you will just be taken for granted by the children. It's not possible for teachers to be too gentle, you really can't be soft-spoken, you have to speak loudly so the children will pay attention, that's my challenge." (IDI-05)

Facing both Difficulties and Rewards in Sharing Wisdom

The theme of encountering both challenges and joy in sharing knowledge reflects the multifaceted nature of mentoring as experienced by seasoned cooperating teachers. Challenges may arise from various sources, such as differences in learning styles between mentor and mentee, navigating through institutional or organizational constraints, or addressing unexpected obstacles in the learning process.

However, alongside these challenges, there is also joy to be found in sharing knowledge. Witnessing the growth and development of a mentee, seeing them grasp new concepts, overcome hurdles, and achieve milestones can be incredibly rewarding. The satisfaction of making a positive impact on someone's learning journey and contributing to their personal and professional growth can bring a profound sense of fulfillment.

Mrs. Vowel2, (pseudonym) candidly shared her experience during her mentoring student teachers wherein she often encounters both challenges and joy in sharing knowledge. Mrs. Vowel2 statement is on the challenges and rewards of dealing with the diverse attitudes of students during mentoring. She acknowledges that students have various attitudes, making it confusing for those who may not claim expertise in handling children. Despite the challenges, Mrs. Vowel finds the experience worthwhile because it allows her to impart knowledge to her students. Additionally, she highlights the importance of this experience for the students themselves, as they may use it when they become teachers in the future. Overall, the statement underscores the complexity of working with diverse student attitudes while emphasizing the value of mentorship in education. where the interview session happened, she said that:

"Malibug ka unsaon pagdeal sa different attitude sa mga student- teacher, dili paman gud sila ingun nga hawod na mo deal sa mga bata, lain lain baya na ug attitude ang mga bata, diverse baya na sila, so experience difficult peru worthy kay happy me maka-impart me ug learning sa ilaha, nga magamit pod nila when they become teacher someday na naa na jud sila sa field of teaching. Mao to sya." (IDI-09)

(Dealing with the different attitudes of students can be confusing, especially when they do not claim to be experts in handling children yet. Children have various attitudes, they are diverse. So, in my experience it is challenging but worthwhile because we are happy to impart knowledge to them. They can also use this experience when they become teachers themselves in the future. That is how it is.)

Similarly with Mrs. Leader, (pseudonym) statement encapsulates the nuanced emotions and experiences that come with being a seasoned cooperating teacher in mentoring. She acknowledges the presence of tiredness, frustration, and challenges, which are inevitable aspects of the mentoring process. Mentoring requires significant time, energy, and patience, and encountering obstacles along the way is not uncommon. However, despite these challenges, what prevails for Mrs. Leader is the happiness derived from her experiences. This happiness stems from the profound sense of fulfillment and satisfaction that comes with being a part of her mentees' learning journeys. Seeing her mentees grow, develop, and succeed brings her immense joy and validates her efforts as a mentor. It was stated that:

"Nindot jud sya nga experience kumbaga mix ng emotion naay kakapoy, usahay malagot ka, ma challenge pod ka but then ang pinaka mopatigbabaw jud sa akoo ang happy ko muna sta akong experience, happy kay naging part ko sa iyahang learning journey." (IDI-03)

(It is really a good experience, like a mix of emotions. There is tiredness, sometimes frustration, and challenges, but what prevails for me is the happiness from my experience. I am happy because I became a part of their learning journey.)

Mrs. Leader's statement reflects the complex mix of emotions that mentoring entails - from the struggles and difficulties to the deep sense of gratification and pride in making a positive impact on others' lives. It highlights the resilience and dedication required to navigate the challenges of mentoring while emphasizing the rewarding nature of guiding and supporting others in their educational journey.

In addition, with Mrs. Diligent, (pseudonym) statement reflects the sense of fulfillment she gains from mentoring student teachers. By providing guidance and instruction, she sees tangible improvement in the student teachers' abilities over time. The satisfaction comes from witnessing their growth from a novice stage to a more competent level. She particularly values the receptiveness of those who are open-minded, as they are more willing to learn and apply her teachings. Overall, Mrs. Diligent finds joy in helping others succeed and takes pride in their accomplishments, which reinforces her own sense of purpose and satisfaction in her role as a seasoned cooperating teacher. She said that:

"Ang akong experience kay fulfilling man pod, teacher ko naay student teacher nga moabut sa akoo, matagaan nako sila ug mga inputs, matudloan nako unsay ilahang mga dapat buhaton, ma feel nimo nga naka tabang ka, labon nag pag-abot sa imoha walang

wala ikaw pa ang ni tudlo ug maayu sa iyaha, unsay buhaton niya at the end of the day as the time na naa sya mag stay sa imoha. Makita nimo nga improve labi natung open-minded pod nga ST, so makahappy sya unya maka proud lang pod sa amoa.” (IDI-13)

(My experience has been fulfilling as a teacher. I have student teachers who come to me, and I can provide them with valuable inputs and guidance on what they need to do. You can really feel that you are helping them, especially when you are the one teaching them well. You see how they improve, especially when they are open-minded. It makes me happy and proud of our work together.)

Mrs. On time (pseudonym) emphasizes the value of her role as a cooperating teacher in guiding student teachers through their preparation for service. She sees herself as a mentor, providing essential insights into the tasks and responsibilities required to excel as educators. Through her guidance, she helps student teachers gain a clear understanding of what is expected of them and how to effectively fulfill their duties in the classroom. Mrs. On Time's experience allows her to offer practical advice and support, ensuring that student teachers are well-prepared for their future roles as educators. It was stated that:

“Akong experience as a cooperating teacher, privilege kay sya as a part sa teacher kay maka tudlo ka sa mga students teacher unsa ang mga angay nga buhaton as a preparation nila sa ilahang service.” (IDI-12)

(My experience as a cooperating teacher is valuable because it allows me to guide student-teachers on what they should do to prepare for their service. It is like being a mentor to them, helping them understand what tasks are necessary to fulfill their role as teachers.)

Handling Teaching Challenges in Creating Lesson Plans

The theme "dealing with pedagogical challenges in instructing on the formulation of lesson plans" underscores the difficulties seasoned cooperating teachers may face when guiding student teachers in this aspect of their training.

One of the challenges is ensuring that lesson plans effectively address diverse student needs and learning styles. This requires understanding how to differentiate instruction and accommodate various learning abilities within the framework of a single lesson plan. In the lesson planning, the seasoned cooperating teachers expressed their encounters with the difficulties when guiding and instructing student teachers or new teachers in creating effective lesson plans. Additionally, there may be challenges in aligning lesson plans with curriculum standards and educational objectives. This involves a deep understanding of the curriculum framework and the ability to translate abstract standards into practical, actionable lesson plans. Another difficulty is helping student teachers develop the skill of anticipating and addressing potential classroom challenges or disruptions within their lesson plans.

Mrs. Casual, (pseudonym) statement sheds light on a specific challenge she faces in mentoring pre-service teachers: checking lesson plans. She acknowledges that for pre-service teachers, particularly those new to structured lesson planning, this aspect can be daunting. Mrs. Casual likely finds it challenging to provide effective guidance on checking lesson plans, especially when balancing the need to focus on both content and grammar. Her difficulty may stem from the need to strike a balance between providing constructive feedback on the structure and content of the lesson plan while also addressing any grammatical errors. Additionally, Mrs. Casual may encounter challenges in helping pre-service teachers understand the importance of thorough and well-structured lesson planning in achieving instructional objectives.

“Specific challenges is checking of lesson plan. As a pre-service teacher mas concern me more on the lesson planning kay sa grammar, din structured nga lesson planning so medyu deraa lang pod ko mas na challenge sa mga naagian nako.” (IDI-04)

(One specific challenge is checking the lesson plan. As a pre-service teacher, I am more concerned about lesson planning than grammar. The structured lesson planning is somewhat new to me, so I find it a bit challenging based on my experiences.)

Overall, Mrs. Casual's experience highlights the importance of providing tailored support and guidance to pre-service teachers as they navigate the complexities of lesson planning. It also underscores the need for patience and understanding when addressing their concerns and difficulties in this area.

Similarly with Mrs. On time, (pseudonym) statement reveals a common challenge faced by cooperating teachers in mentoring: ensuring alignment between lesson plans and instructional objectives. She mentions that despite guiding student teachers on creating lesson plans and selecting appropriate resources, there are instances where parts of their plans do not align with their objectives. This discrepancy poses a challenge for Mrs. On Time as a mentor. The difficulty lies in helping student teachers understand the importance of coherence and alignment in lesson planning. Mrs. On Time likely finds herself needing to provide additional guidance and clarification to help student teachers identify and rectify these mismatches. This may involve revisiting the instructional objectives, refining the structure of the lesson plan, and selecting more suitable resources to support learning outcomes effectively.

“My experience usually pagcooperating teacher ka magmentor ka kung unsa ang paagi sa paghimo ug lesson plan, unsa ang gamiton nila. Naay mga part sa ilang plan nga sukwahi pa ilang objectives, so kana nga way isa na sa challenge as a mentor.” (IDI-12)

(In my experience as a cooperating teacher, mentoring involves guiding on how to create a lesson plan and what resources to use. Sometimes, parts of their plans do not align with their objectives, which becomes a challenge as a mentor.)

In addition with Mrs. Last (pseudonym) statement highlights the persistent challenge of lesson planning for both student teachers and seasoned cooperating teachers alike. Despite having received training and seminars on lesson planning prior to entering the field, Mrs.

Last acknowledges that the actual implementation of lesson planning in the classroom setting presents unique difficulties. The discrepancy between theoretical knowledge and practical application becomes evident when cooperating teachers like Mrs. Last find themselves grappling with the complexities of lesson planning in real-world scenarios. She emphasizes that the challenges of lesson planning persist even after years of experience, indicating that it's an ongoing struggle for many educators.

“The most challenging part is the lesson planning, although you already learn that one in your seminars, mga trainings before mag adtu dere sa field, but for us cooperating teacher sa kadugay dugay most challenging gihapon ang lesson plan. Although naay trainings maka ingun man pod sila nga little bit raman gud ma'am, lahi raman jud kung actual. Lesson planning is the number one.” (IDI-14)

(The most challenging aspect is lesson planning, even though you have learned it in seminars and trainings before entering the field. For us cooperating teachers, even after a long time, lesson planning remains the most challenging. Despite the trainings, some may say it is just a little bit different, ma'am, but it is really different when it is actual. Lesson planning is the number one challenge.)

Lastly, Mrs. Short hair (pseudonym), she is conveying her frustration with the inadequacies she observed in the lesson planning skills of some pre-service teachers. She emphasizes that while many student teachers have not yet been properly introduced to lesson planning. She then illustrates her point with an anecdote about a specific student teacher she mentored. Despite providing clear instructions and checking the completion of the task, the student teacher exhibited confusion and forgetfulness when asked to recall the instructions. This situation frustrates Mrs. Short hair because she feels that she has already gone over the instructions and checked the work, yet the student teacher still struggles to remember or understand them.

“As my experience as a seasoned cooperating teacher and mentoring pre-service teacher, naa pay student teacher nga wala pa na introduce ang lesson plan...permero nakong ST kay labad kaayu tudloan og lesson planning, gi instruct na "ma'am unsa gani to?" "huh!?"... "unsa!?, humana man kog instruct nimo niya gi-checkan na nako tanan", pa utrohon na pod ko niya kay nakalimot”. (IDI-05)

(In my experience as a seasoned cooperating teacher and mentoring pre-service teachers, there are still student teachers who have not been introduced to lesson planning yet... my first student teacher whom I had to teach lesson planning; I instructed her, and when I checked, everything was completed. But when I repeated the instructions, she looked confused and said, "Ma'am, what was that again?" "Huh?"..."What!?! I just finished instructing you, and I already checked everything," I said, repeating the instructions because she forgot.)

The example provided illustrates a common issue faced by cooperating teachers, where despite providing clear instructions, student teachers may struggle to retain the information or understand the broader context of lesson planning.

Handling Behaviors Atypical in the Student-Teacher Dynamic

The theme of handling atypical behaviors in the student-teacher dynamic relates to the challenges experienced by seasoned cooperating teachers when mentoring pre-service teachers. In this context, atypical behaviors could encompass a wide range of issues, such as lack of understanding of lesson planning, difficulty in following instructions, or struggles with classroom management. Cooperating teachers encounter pre-service teachers who exhibit behaviors that are unexpected or unusual within the student-teacher relationship. These behaviors can pose difficulties for the cooperating teacher in effectively mentoring and guiding the pre-service teacher. This could include instances where student teachers exhibit behaviors such as lack of initiative, resistance to feedback, or difficulty in following instructions, which can challenge the dynamics of the teaching and learning process.

In looking back on her experiences, Mr. Short hair (pseudonym) is expressing her frustration with the challenges she faces in mentoring student teachers who exhibit a range of behaviors that hinder their effectiveness in the classroom. She highlights two specific difficulties she has encountered: A student teacher who was stricter than her: Mrs. Short hair likely found it challenging to mentor a student teacher who adopted a stricter approach to teaching than her own. This dynamic may have led to conflicts or differences in teaching styles, making it challenging for Mrs. Short hair to effectively guide the student teacher in finding a balanced and appropriate approach to classroom management. Student teachers becoming too relaxed or lazy: Mrs. Short hair observes that some student teachers become complacent and lazy over time, neglecting the preparation and use of instructional materials in their lessons. Despite being instructed on the importance of instructional materials by school administrators, these student teachers fail to meet expectations, which Mrs. Short hair attributes to laziness.

“Naka encounter ko ug student teacher nga mas strikta pa sa akona, naa poy mga tapulan nga kung mag prepare silag lesson naa na na silag Instructional materials peru karon kay wala na relax na kaayu, kuha lag libro...katung sa permero nga cycle wala naka prepare-medyo tapulanon jud no.” (IDI-05)

(I encountered a student teacher who was stricter than me. Some are lazy; when they prepare a lesson, they might have instructional materials, but now they have become too relaxed. They just grab a book...It is like in the first cycle, they were not prepared—quite lazy, right?)

Overall, Mrs. Short hair's statement reflects the difficulties she experiences in mentoring student teachers who exhibit varying levels of readiness, commitment, and professionalism. She faces challenges in navigating differences in teaching styles and in motivating

student teachers to maintain high standards of preparation and professionalism in their teaching practice.

In the case of Mrs. Diligent, (pseudonym) describing a common difficulty experienced in mentoring, which is dealing with close-mindedness in the mentee. She expresses frustration with mentees who insist on doing things their way and are resistant to considering alternative approaches or suggestions. This close-mindedness manifests in several ways.

Reluctance to seek out information. The mentee may claim to be seeking information, but in reality, they only seek out sources or perspectives that align with their preconceived notions or preferred methods. They may not actively seek diverse perspectives or input from their mentor or other sources. Disappointment with alternative suggestions: When presented with suggestions or feedback that deviates from their preferred approach, the mentee reacts negatively. They may become disappointed or frustrated, indicating a lack of openness to new ideas or perspectives. Inability to adapt: Mrs. Diligent notes that the mentee seems unable or unwilling to adapt to suggestions. Instead of incorporating feedback or adjusting their approach based on new information, they cling rigidly to their own methods, even if those methods are not yielding the desired results.

"Close minded, kana ganing imo ng gihungit ang mgdapat buhatom, imo ng gihungit tanan nga information , tanan nga dapat niyang sundon peru dismayado ka kay murag wala syay nadungog, murag wala niya nakita, kana bang dili niya e adapt ang imohang suggestion." (IDI-13)

(Close-mindedness, when someone insists on doing things their way, they seek out information, but they are disappointed if they do not hear or see it, as if they cannot adapt to your suggestions.)

Overall, Mrs. Diligent statement highlights the challenge of mentoring individuals who exhibit close-mindedness, as it impedes the mentor-mentee relationship and inhibits the mentee's growth and development.

In addition, with Mrs. Eye glass (pseudonym), expressing her frustration with the lack of initiative she encounters when mentoring pre-service teachers. She highlights a significant difficulty in her mentoring experience, which is the observation that many pre-service teachers lack the proactive drive to take on tasks or responsibilities without direct assignment. Her statement suggests that these pre-service teachers rely heavily on explicit instructions and guidance from their mentor, and they do not demonstrate independent initiative in seeking out opportunities for growth or taking ownership of their learning process. Mrs. Eye glass finds this lack of initiative particularly frustrating, as it requires her to constantly assign tasks and provide direction, rather than fostering a more self-directed and motivated approach to learning and professional development.

"Walay initiative, mao jud nay pinaka hate nako na, walay initiative na pre-service nga nagkapuliki naka tungod kay wala ko naghatag sa imohag task dili ka mo puli, mao jud na walay initiative." (IDI-06)

(Lack of initiative, that is what I hate the most. Pre-service teachers lacking initiative; if I do not assign them a task, they will not do anything. That is a complete lack of initiative.)

Mrs. Vowel2 (pseudonym), describing a challenging experience she had while mentoring a student teacher during the last school year. The student teacher in question displayed a lack of initiative and responsibility in managing the classroom environment. Despite being in a position of authority and responsibility, the student teacher would sit in the front of the classroom, engrossed in their cellphone, even when the students were being disruptive or too loud. Mrs. Vowel2 expresses frustration with the student teacher's passive approach to classroom management. Instead of taking proactive steps to address student behavior or engage with the class, the student teacher seemed indifferent and relied on Mrs. Vowel2 to take charge and resolve any issues that arose.

This lack of initiative and accountability is a significant difficulty for Mrs. Vowel2 in her role as a mentor. She expects student teachers to actively participate in classroom management and demonstrate a willingness to take ownership of their responsibilities. The behavior of the student teacher in this scenario reflects a broader challenge in mentoring, where some pre-service teachers struggle to assert themselves and take on leadership roles in the classroom.

"Mag based ko last school year, so dili lang jud ko magmention ug ngalan, naay na under sa akona na student teacher nga kana bitawng bisan naa sya sa front mag segeg cellphone unya bisan saba na kaayu ang mga bata wala syay paki alam unya maghulat lang ba nga moingon nga ikaw sa bahala sa classroom, murag wala gani syay initiative." (IDI-09)

(Based on last school year, I will not mention names, but there was a student teacher under me who would sit in the front, engrossed in their cellphone, even when the students were being too loud. They would not care and would just wait for me to take charge of the classroom. It is like they did not have any initiative.)

Mrs. Vowel2 observed that the student teacher would remain absorbed in their cellphone, even when the students were being disruptive, indicating a lack of proactive approach to managing the classroom environment. Instead, the student teacher seemed to rely on Mrs. Vowel2 to take charge and address any issues that arose, suggesting a deficiency in leadership and initiative.

Guiding Student-Teachers to Improve Classroom Management Skills Due to Inexperience

As experienced by seasoned cooperating teachers, revolves around the need to provide support to student teachers in improving their classroom management skills due to their lack of experience. These seasoned teachers likely observed that student teachers often

struggle with effectively managing a classroom environment, which can hinder the learning experience for students and create challenges for both the student teacher and the cooperating teacher

Mrs. Red, (pseudonym) highlights the significant challenge she faces as a seasoned cooperating teacher: managing children's behavior in a way that ensures they listen and respond appropriately. Mrs. Red emphasizes the necessity of using a commanding tone and authority to establish control and gain the attention of the students. This experience underscores the common struggle among educators, especially student teachers, in effectively managing classroom behavior and gaining respect from students.

"Sometimes you need to raise your voice nga madunggan ka nila ba dapat you have to put command sa imong voice nga motoo ang bata. So mao rajud na ang number one nga challenges sa akoo sa mga ST nga unsaon pagpabehave ang bata, maminaw bitaw sila sa imoha, you act gina ingnan nako sya nga act as a teacher." (IDI-01)

(Sometimes you need to raise your voice, so they will hear you, you have to put command in your voice so the children believe you, that's really the number one challenge for me as a seasoned cooperating teacher, how to manage the behavior of the children so they'll listen to you, I tell them to act as a teacher.)

In addition, with Mrs. Vowel2, (pseudonym) focus of statement is on the challenge of building trust and authority with students as a student teacher. Despite having the ability to effectively manage classroom behavior, student teachers often struggle to gain the trust and respect of their students. Mrs. Vowel2 highlights the paradox where student teachers, despite being able to control the children's behavior, still face difficulties in earning the trust and confidence of their students.

"Paghandle nila sa classroom management, naa man gud pag ang mga bata man gud dili gud kaayo motoo sila sa student teacher, mao jud to sya challenge jud na sya sa amoa nga maparehas gani sila sa amoa nga ma control namo ang bata ba niya mahadlok pa baya ni sila mga saba, ana ba kay syempre kay graded ana siguro". (IDI-09)

(That is the only thing they handle in classroom management, the children do not really trust the student teachers much, it is really a challenge for us, they are just like us, we can control the children, and they are still afraid of getting scolded because, of course, they are still graded.)

Mrs. Short Hair (pseudonym), statement is on the importance of assertiveness in the classroom and the challenges associated with finding the right balance between being too gentle and being assertive enough to command the attention and respect of students. Mrs. Short Hair highlights the variability in children's responses to different teaching styles and behaviors, emphasizing the need for teachers to assert themselves in order to avoid being taken for granted by students. She underscores the idea that being overly gentle or soft-spoken may not effectively capture students' attention or command respect, especially in situations where assertiveness is required to manage behavior or maintain order in the classroom.

"Lahi2 jud man jud ang bata no makaingon jud kag sobra or leaded jud kaayu, maka ingon jud kag moulbo imong kaspa pag ing-ani ang mga student. So karon kung dika isog dere sa imong classroom wala jud irokon ra jud ka sa mga bata. Dili pwede sa mga maestra ang hilomon, dili jud ka pwede kung hinay ang voice dapat kusog jud ka para ang bata nga di na maninaw sa imo ma caught iyang attention" (IDI-05)

(Children really vary, they can say you are too much or too loaded, they can say you are overreacting, when a student acts like this. So now, if you are not assertive in your classroom, you will just be taken for granted by the children. It is not possible for teachers to be too gentle, you really cannot be soft-spoken, you have to speak loudly so the children will pay attention, that's my challenge.)

Research Question No. 2: How do seasoned cooperating teachers cope with the challenges they encounter in mentoring pre-service teachers?

The focus of question is to understand the strategies and approaches seasoned cooperating teachers employ to navigate the challenges they face in mentoring pre-service teachers. This question aims to delve into the specific methods, techniques, and support systems that experienced educators utilize to effectively mentor and support pre-service teachers during their practicum or student teaching experiences.

By exploring how seasoned cooperating teachers cope with these challenges, the research seeks to identify best practices, insights, and potential areas for improvement in the mentorship process. This question ultimately aims to contribute to the enhancement of mentorship programs for pre-service teachers, thereby facilitating their professional development and ensuring a successful transition into the teaching profession. From the answer of the participants, 4 themes emerged: feedbacking, consulting time, practicing open communication and feedbacking, consulting with colleagues for advice and processing the student-teacher self-reflection for guidance.

Balancing and Managing Time

Seasoned cooperating teacher in mentoring student teachers revolves around helping their mentees develop essential time management skills to effectively handle the demands of teaching. This includes guiding student teachers in prioritizing tasks, allocating time for lesson planning, grading, classroom management, professional development, and personal well-being. Additionally, seasoned cooperating teachers may demonstrate how to adapt to unexpected changes in schedule or teaching strategies while maintaining

productivity. They aim to instill in student teachers the importance of maintaining a healthy work-life balance and avoiding burnout by managing their time wisely.

Table 3. *Coping Mechanism for the Challenges Faced by Seasoned Cooperating teacher in Mentoring Student-Teacher*

<i>Emerging themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statement</i>
Balancing and Managing Time	<p>"Balance in the sense that after modeling, I'll be the first to lead; with 7 subjects, one subject is for her and the other 6 will be mine. So, it could be balanced in that way, allowing for some time, albeit limited, which still has a significant impact for me to correct what is wrong in their teaching. For instance, if the class has not started yet, especially in the morning, that is when I'll talk to them; in the afternoon, we'll have time too, not just worrying about it while they're busy with other tasks like preparing materials or asking question." (IDI-01)</p> <p>"It is all about time management; you should know how to manage your time. I allocate time for my student teachers; for example, if they need assistance, I make sure to give them time because they come to our school to train, to master teaching skills. Even if I am busy, because teachers are always multitasking, I make sure to allocate time that can help them. Time management." (IDI-13)</p> <p>We also balance the children's learning so we do not neglect them; I won't abandon the children, and they won't be neglected either." (IDI-06)</p> <p>"Of course, effective time management while mentoring includes observation and feedback sessions. So, I set goals for my student teacher, like from 3:30 to 4:30, that is our feedback time about my observations of her, and she should also participate and consider my suggestions." (IDI-11)</p>
Practicing Open Communication and Feedbacking	<p>There is only number one for me, there should be a constant communication, for me it is very important, personal message, talk-what are the problem, what are the challenges encountered, what are the things that you wanted to ask, it must have an open communication from the student teacher to the cooperating teacher." (IDI-14)</p> <p>"Having open communication to establish open honest and regular communication. The student teacher share feedback and address any concern or she's so we also have a planning to gather collaborate and lesson planning what method should be used on the specific subject provide guidance and share for sure experiences." (IDI-11)</p> <p>"Talk about it, then what to help the student teacher then look for a solution... We plan together inquiring together what are the deficiencies what should be improved then if there are conflicts look for resolutions... provide feedback." (IDI-08)</p> <p>"Usually before going home...just having a conversation...I'll make her realize and then she'll be ahead next time around just talking over a cup of coffee, not to say that directly afterward like formal good, just talking normal conversation." (IDI-03)</p>
Consulting with Colleagues for Advice	<p>"If I mention a support system, my co-teacher in grade level... We consult each other, like, 'Ma'am Weng, is my colleague... she's also part of my support system. Then, our master teacher, because we ask our master teacher rather than our principal." (IDI-09)</p> <p>"A support system, meaning colleagues are a big help, especially during focus group discussions where we share and learn from each other. It should be like that. In that way, you can also learn from your colleagues or your principal because they can also guide us. They are the backbone, our support system, which can improve us and help you too." (IDI-14)</p> <p>"As a cooperating teacher, our colleagues and mentorship programs are very helpful. My colleagues are the ones I mentioned earlier. We ask each other questions, brainstorm our thoughts, what tools to use, like in lesson planning, if I struggle or have doubts about the flow, I can go to a master teacher because they are the ones who are updated with the latest knowledge. So, I should seek their experiences, their advice, and discuss challenges with fellow educators." (IDI-11)</p> <p>"A support system, maybe my colleagues here, we're in grade 5. So, my co-teachers in grade 5, we talk and observe each other, like what I noticed about her, and what she noticed about me, what can help us improve further as student teachers." (IDI-04)</p>
Processing the Student-Teacher Self-Reflection for Guidance	<p>"I process why it turned out like that? What seems to be the problem on your end? Let them realize, How's your demo teaching?...What could be the factor there? Do you think that is difficult? What is your reflection? Apparently, we really need to prepare permanently, we should manage our time properly, our attitude towards work should be positive, that's one aspect addressed." (IDI-03)</p> <p>"I help them through self-reflection, so I encourage them to reflect on their own beliefs about teaching... what kind of teachers they aspire to be. I would say they should reflect and self-assess, so mentors should take time to reflect on the situation and self-assess their own actions and approaches, so we also reflect on whether we are effective and if we can provide support." (IDI-11)</p> <p>"For me, I let them perform their duties in their own ways and according to their own abilities, but with my guidance. I give them the freedom to perform, to do whatever they want to do, especially in classroom management and teaching and learning." (IDI-14)</p>

Mrs. Red (pseudonym) statement suggests that she aims to maintain a balanced approach to mentoring by ensuring she takes the lead in guiding her mentees while also allowing them space to develop their own skills and responsibilities. She plans to allocate specific time slots for individual attention to each mentee, ensuring they receive adequate support and feedback. By addressing issues promptly, such as during the morning before classes start, she intends to maintain a proactive stance in correcting any teaching shortcomings. Additionally, she emphasizes the importance of utilizing available time in the afternoons for mentoring sessions, rather than solely focusing on administrative tasks or material preparation. Overall, Mrs. Red's approach highlights the significance of time management

and proactive engagement in effectively supporting her mentees' growth and development.

"Balance in the sense na after sa modeling ako man gyud ang mag una, 7 subject one subject lang iyaha akoa 6 subject mana. So mahimo syang balance... gamay nga time peru dako syag impact para sa akoa na ma correct bitaw dayun ang kung unsay mali sa imong ST... sugod ang klase labi nag morning imo na syang sultian, pagkahapon na pod me time dili ingun nga nag dibdiban kana ra gung while nag pilit² nag gunting² niya magpangutana." (IDI -01)

(Balance in the sense that after modeling, I will be the first to lead; with 7 subjects, one subject is for her and the other 6 will be mine. So, it could be balanced... allowing for some time, albeit limited, which still has a significant impact for me to correct what is wrong in their teaching...if the class has not started yet, especially in the morning, that's when I'll talk to them; in the afternoon, we will have time too, not just worrying about it while they're busy with other tasks like preparing materials or asking question.)

In addition, the focus of Mrs. Diligent (pseudonym) statement is on the importance of time management in coping with the challenges of mentoring student teachers. She emphasizes the need for both her and the student teachers to effectively manage their time. Mrs. Diligent allocates time specifically for assisting her student teachers, recognizing that they are at the school to train and master teaching skills. Despite being busy with multitasking, she ensures that she sets aside time to support and help them. Overall, the statement underscores the significance of prioritizing time and allocating it efficiently to meet the needs of student teachers during their training.

"Time management lang jud, dapat kabalo jud ka mo manage sa imong oras, akoa kay tagaan nakog oras akong ST, halimbawa kailangan niya ang assistance muhatag gyud tag time kay ni anhi mana sila sa atong school to train, to master unsaon pagtudlo so bisan pag unsa ka busy kay ang teacher multitasking man gyud na, mo exert jud tag time nga maka help sa ilaha, time management." (IDI-13)

(It is all about time management; you should know how to manage your time. I allocate time for my student teachers; for example, if they need assistance, I make sure to give them time because they come to our school to train, to master teaching skills. Even if I am busy, because teachers are always multitasking, I make sure to allocate time that can help them. Time management.)

Mr. Diligent, (pseudonym) statement reflects her commitment to a collaborative and balanced approach to mentoring. She plans to actively engage in teaching herself to lighten the workload of her mentees, while also ensuring they have opportunities to teach and be observed by her. This approach emphasizes mutual support and continuous learning, rather than taking turns or simply delegating tasks. By maintaining this balance between teaching responsibilities and mentorship, Mrs. Diligent aims to prevent any neglect of the children's educational needs. Additionally, her statement emphasizes the importance of accountability for both herself and her mentees in ensuring the children receive the attention and guidance they require for their development. Overall, Mrs. Diligent's approach prioritizes teamwork, active involvement, and the well-being of the children under their care.

"Ako moana man ko nga, ako sa ron na magtudlo, gaan nako sila ug mga trabahoon din sa st napod ko mag-atubang, din ikaw na pod didtu magtudlo ako na pod dere magtan-aw sa imoha, di puli puli me, na balance namo ang amoang trabaho na balance pod namo ang learning sa bata dili na namo mabyaan ang mga bata, di nako mabyaan ng bata di pod niya ma biyaan." (IDI-06)

"I will be the one to teach now, I will lighten their tasks, and when it's time for me to face them, you will also teach there, and I will also observe you. We will not take turns; we will balance our work and also balance our teaching with the children so that we won't neglect them. I won't neglect the child, and the child won't be neglected by you either."

Furthermore Mrs. Hairband (pseudonym), emphasizes setting clear goals for her student teacher and allocating specific time slots. Mrs. Hairband approach prioritizes regular and structured feedback sessions to provide guidance and support to the student teacher. By establishing dedicated time for feedback, she ensures that there is focused attention on addressing teaching strengths and areas for improvement. Mrs. Hairband's emphasis on structured feedback sessions highlights the importance of ongoing evaluation and collaboration in the mentorship process.

"Of course the effective time management while mentoring such as observation and feedbacking session so mag set me ni Ma'am ug goal akong ST nga ma'am 3:30-4:30 atoa nang feedback time about my observation sa imoha, so dapat siya mo apil pod unsa iyang suggestion." (IDI-11)

(Of course, effective time management while mentoring includes observation and feedback sessions. So, I set goals for my student teacher, like from 3:30 to 4:30, that is our feedback time about my observations of her, and she should also participate and consider my suggestions.)

Practicing Open Communication and Feedbacking

The theme of practicing open communication and feedbacking in mentoring highlights the importance of establishing clear channels for communication and providing constructive feedback to support the growth and development of both the mentor and the mentee.

In the context of a seasoned cooperating teacher coping with challenges in mentoring, this theme suggests that they prioritize open and honest communication with their mentees. This involves creating an environment where mentees feel comfortable expressing their concerns, asking questions, and seeking guidance. Additionally, the seasoned cooperating teacher actively provides feedback to their

mentees, both in terms of their teaching practices and their overall professional growth. This feedback is constructive, specific, and geared towards helping the mentees improve their skills and effectiveness in the classroom. By emphasizing open communication and feedback, the seasoned cooperating teacher fosters a supportive and collaborative relationship with their mentees, which ultimately enhances the mentoring process and contributes to the success of both parties.

Mrs. Last, (pseudonym) prioritizes being present for her student teachers, offering assistance, advice, and feedback whenever needed. She understands the significance of being a reliable source of support, especially during challenging moments or when student teachers encounter obstacles. Additionally, Mrs. Last emphasizes the need for patience and understanding, recognizing that every student teacher progresses at their own pace and may require different levels of support. Overall, the main focus of this theme experienced by Mrs. Last is on nurturing a supportive mentorship relationship that empowers student teachers to thrive and succeed in their teaching journey.

"There's only number one for me, there should be a constant communication, for me it is very important, personal message, talk-what are the problem, what are the challenges encountered, what are the things that you wanted to ask, it must have an open communication from the student teacher to the cooperating teacher." (IDI-14)

Similarly with Mrs. Hairband, (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of open and honest communication as a crucial strategy for coping with the challenges of mentoring. She underscores the need for mentors to establish regular and transparent communication channels with student teachers, encouraging them to share feedback, concerns, and ideas openly. Additionally, Mrs. Hairband highlights the significance of collaborative planning sessions where both the mentor and student teacher can discuss and strategize lesson plans together, ensuring alignment with specific subject requirements. Furthermore, she stresses the importance of providing guidance and sharing relevant experiences, either as an expert or from personal teaching experiences, to support the development of student teachers. Lastly, Mrs. Hairband emphasizes the value of regular observation and constructive feedback on the teaching practices of student teachers, facilitating continuous improvement and growth in the mentoring process. Overall, the statement underscores the role of effective communication, collaboration, and feedback in navigating the complexities of mentoring.

"Having open communication to establish open honest and regular communication... Ug sa ST share feedback and address any concern or she's so we also have a planning to gather collaborate and lesson planning unsa nga method ang dapat gamiton on the specific subject provide guidance and share for sure experiences..." (IDI-11)

(Having open communication helps establish honest and regular conversations. In ST, we share feedback and address any concerns. We also plan to collaborate and do lesson planning, discussing which methods should be used for specific subjects. We provide guidance and share experiences to ensure success.)

In addition, Mrs. Happy (pseudonym) emphasizes open communication by encouraging discussion about issues, jointly identifying areas for improvement, and actively involving the student teacher in problem-solving and decision-making processes. Mrs. Happy emphasizes the importance of addressing conflicts and providing constructive feedback to both the student teacher and the students, with the ultimate goal of facilitating a positive learning environment and professional growth for all parties involved.

"Talk about it, then ano tabangan ang ST then mangitag solution... Mag-planning ming duha din mag-inquiring together unsay mga kulang...then kung naay mga conflict mangita dayon meg mga resolusyon... mag feedbacking." (IDI-08)

(Talk about it, then what to help the student teacher then look for a solution... We plan together inquiring together what are the deficiencies what should be improved then if there are conflicts look for resolutions... provide feedback.)

Moreover, Mrs. Leader (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of informal, open communication as a method for addressing challenges encountered in mentoring. She describes a scenario where she and her mentee engage in casual conversations, often over a cup of coffee or a meal, before going home after class. During these moments, they discuss various topics in a relaxed setting, allowing Mrs. Leader to subtly address any challenges her mentee may be facing. By framing these discussions as informal conversations rather than formal feedback sessions, Mrs. Leader creates a comfortable environment where her mentees feel at ease sharing their concerns and seeking advice. Through these interactions, Mrs. Leader can gently guide her mentee, helping them recognize and address challenges without the pressure of a formal evaluation.

"Usually before uwian...istorya istorya lang...ipa-realize nako sa iyaha and then mauna siya tong next time around istorya over a cup of coffee, dili ingon nga kanang direct paghuman murag formal good, istorya istorya lang normal conversation..." (IDI-03)

(Usually before going home, we just talk... I make them realize things, and then next time we talk over a cup of coffee. It is not like a formal discussion after everything; it is just casual conversation.)

Overall, Mrs. Leader's approach to coping with challenges in mentoring involves fostering a supportive and communicative relationship with her mentee through informal conversations, ultimately promoting mutual growth and development.

Consulting with Colleagues for Advice

This theme in the context of seasoned cooperating teachers coping with mentoring challenges involves actively seeking guidance, support, and feedback from other experienced educators. When faced with difficulties in mentoring, such as managing diverse student

needs, addressing behavioral issues, or implementing effective teaching strategies, seasoned cooperating teachers can draw upon the expertise and insights of their colleagues. This may involve informal conversations, formal mentorship programs, or participation in professional learning communities where teachers share experiences, exchange ideas, and collaborate on solutions. By leveraging the collective knowledge and experience of their peers, seasoned cooperating teachers can enhance their mentoring effectiveness, develop new skills, and ultimately support the growth and success of the student teachers under their guidance.

Mrs. Vowel2, (pseudonym) underscores the importance of building a support system within the grade level to cope with the challenges of mentoring, especially in a small team where resources and expertise may be limited. By mentioning Ma'am Weng, her colleague, and their master teacher, she highlights how they consult each other and seek guidance from a more experienced educator within their immediate professional circle. This approach enables Mrs. Vowel2 to tap into a network of support, share insights, and collaboratively problem-solve, ultimately enhancing her ability to mentor effectively despite the constraints of a small team.

Additionally, her preference for consulting their master teacher over the principal suggests a recognition of the specialized knowledge and practical experience that their mentor can provide, further emphasizing the importance of seeking guidance from within the teaching community. Overall, Mrs. Vowel2's statement reflects a proactive approach to addressing mentoring challenges through collaboration and leveraging existing expertise within her professional network.

"Kung moingon pod kug support system, pwede kauban nako sa grade level.. magpangutan-anay me ana niya ma'am weng akong kauban ba, ana ana gud, usa pod na sya sa akong support system, then among master teacher kay mas didtu man gud me mag ask sa among master teacher kay sa kaning among principal..." (IDI-09)

(If I mention a support system, my co-teacher in grade level... We consult each other, like, 'Ma'am Weng, is my colleague... she's also part of my support system. Then, our master teacher, because we ask our master teacher rather than our principal...)

On the other hand, Mrs. Last, (pseudonym) underscores the vital role of a robust support system, particularly emphasizing the value of colleagues and mentors in coping with mentoring challenges. She highlights the importance of collaborative learning through activities like focus group discussions, where educators can share experiences, exchange ideas, and learn from one another. Mrs. Last acknowledges the significant contributions of colleagues and principals as part of the backbone and support system for teachers, emphasizing how they can guide and improve each other's practice. Mrs. Last emphasis on collaborative learning and mentorship within a supportive community impacts the effectiveness of mentoring programs, teacher development, and overall job satisfaction.

"Support system, meaning mga colleagues dako pod kayong tabang syempre kung naay mga FGD mag sharing, mag kuan me, ahing-ani pod siguro dapat. So in that way maka learn pod ka from your outhor or your colleagues especially the principal naa sya ika kuan sa amoa, so nga kana pod sila ang mga backbone, mga support system pod namo, in which maka improve pod sa amoa nga maka help pod to sa imoha." (IDI-14)

(A support system, meaning colleagues are a big help, especially during focus group discussions where we share and learn from each other. It should be like that. In that way, you can also learn from your colleagues or your principal because they can also guide us. They are the backbone, our support system, which can improve us and help you too.)

In addition, with Mrs. Hairband (pseudonym) the statement is on the importance of self-reflection and self-assessment as strategies for coping with the challenges of mentoring. She emphasizes the need for student teachers to reflect on their own beliefs about teaching philosophy, the purpose of education, effective teaching methods, and the type of teachers they aspire to become. Mrs. Hairband encourages mentors to guide student teachers in this process of self-reflection and self-assessment. Furthermore, she highlights the significance of mentors themselves engaging in reflection and self-assessment to evaluate the effectiveness of their actions and approaches in providing support to student teachers. Overall, the statement emphasizes the value of introspection and self-evaluation as tools for growth and improvement in the mentoring process.

"So as a cooperating teacher dako kaayu ug tabang ning naatay colleagues and mentorship programs, so colleagues moto akong giingun kagaina kung naatay mga. Pangutana naatay lawa lawa sa atoang mga huna²unsaon ni, unsay tool nga gamiton ani si ma'am, kung kanang sa lesson planning kung maglisod kog checking, kung naa koy dili sure kung tama ba ng flow unya ako dili pod ko sure pwede kaayu ko mo adtu sa nga master teacher ma'am, kay sila man gyuy naka eskwela ani no ang mga latest nahibal-an gyud na sa mga master teachers, so mao to, dapat e seek nako ilahang mga experiences ilahang mga advises and discuss challenges also with fellow educators mao ratu ma'am." (IDI-11)

(As a cooperating teacher, our colleagues and mentorship programs are very helpful. We ask each other questions, brainstorm our thoughts, what tools to use, like in lesson planning, if I struggle or have doubts about the flow, I can go to a master teacher because they are the ones who are updated with the latest knowledge. So, I should seek their experiences, their advice, and discuss challenges with fellow educators.)

Lastly, Mrs. Casual, (pseudonym) evolves around the concept of peer support and observation as a means to cope with the challenges of mentoring. observation with colleagues, particularly those teaching the same grade level, they create a supportive network where they can share insights, provide feedback, and learn from each other's experiences. Mrs. Casual emphasizes the value of mutual observation and feedback as key strategies to further enhance their effectiveness in mentoring and teaching.

"Support system, siguro ano akong nga kauban dere, kami grade 5 ana gud, so akong mga co-teachers sa grade 5, ana lang kay ga sturya man pod me ug mao ba akong namatikdan ani niya, mao ba akoang na kanang, siya pod unsay na matikdan niya ani, ana unsay ikatabang pasa mas ma improve pa ang mga ST." (IDI 04)

(A support system, maybe my colleagues here, we're in grade 5. So, my co-teachers in grade 5, we talk and observe each other, like what I noticed about her, and what she noticed about me, what can help us improve further as student teachers.)

Processing the Student-Teacher Self-reflection for Guidance

Seasoned cooperating teacher, coping with challenges in mentoring often involves a deep level of self-reflection to navigate the complexities of the role. This entails examining past mentoring experiences, identifying patterns of success and areas for improvement, and being open to adapting strategies to meet the needs of each unique student teacher. Self-reflection allows the seasoned teacher to assess their own biases, assumptions, and communication styles, enabling them to better support and guide student teachers through any challenges they may encounter. It also helps the seasoned teacher maintain a growth mindset, staying open to learning and evolving as a mentor. Ultimately, self-reflection serves as a guiding tool for seasoned cooperating teachers to effectively navigate the mentoring process and cultivate a positive and supportive learning environment for their student teachers.

Mrs. Leader (pseudonym), emphasizes the need for student teachers to critically analyze their actions and outcomes, particularly in situations where things don't go as planned. Mrs. Leader encourages asking probing questions to understand the root causes of issues and to identify areas for improvement. By guiding student teachers through this process of self-reflection and analysis, Mrs. Leader aims to cultivate a mindset of continuous learning and growth. The focus is on developing skills in time management, preparation, and maintaining a positive attitude towards work, which are essential aspects for success in teaching and mentoring roles.

"E process nako nganong naingana? Unsa imohang problema?... e pa realize... How's your demo teaching? Unsa kahay factor didto? so do you think is that difficult? Unsay reflection nimo? Need jud diay ma'am mag prepare permanenti, dapat e management gyud nato ang time dapat positive gyud atong attitude towards to work...isa na sya nga ma adress." (IDI 03)

(I process why it turned out like that? What seems to be the problem on your end? let them realize, How's your demo teaching?...What could be the factor there? do you think that's difficult? What is your reflection? Apparently, we really need to prepare permanently, we should manage our time properly, our attitude towards work should be positive, that is one aspect addressed.)

On the other hand, Mrs. Hairband (pseudonym) statement focus on the importance of self-reflection and introspection as essential tools for coping with the challenges of mentoring. She emphasizes the significance of guiding student teachers to reflect on their own beliefs and philosophies about teaching, including the purpose of education, effective teaching methods, and their aspirations as educators. Mrs. Hairband underscores the idea that through self-reflection and self-assessment, student teachers can develop a deeper understanding of their teaching practices and goals. Additionally, she highlights the role of mentors in facilitating this process by encouraging student teachers to reflect on their experiences and guiding them in evaluating their actions and approaches. Ultimately, the statement emphasizes the value of continual self-reflection and assessment for both student teachers and mentors in fostering growth and improvement in the mentoring relationship.

"I help them through a self reflection, so I encourage reflect on their own belief... what kind of teachers do they aspire to be. I would say reflect and self assess so mentors take time to reflect on the situation and self-assess their own action and approaches so kami pod mo reflect pod me effective ba me makahatag ba me ug support." (IDI-11)

(I help them through self-reflection, so I encourage them to reflect on their own beliefs about teaching...what kind of teachers they aspire to be. I would say they should reflect and self-assess, so mentors should take time to reflect on the situation and self-assess their own actions and approaches, so we also reflect on whether we are effective and if we can provide support.)

Furthermore, Mrs. Last, (pseudonym) emphasizes allowing student teachers to perform their duties according to their own abilities and preferences, while still providing mentorship and support. Mrs. Last believes in giving student teachers the freedom to experiment and explore different approaches to classroom management and teaching methods. By offering guidance alongside this freedom, she aims to empower student teachers to take ownership of their teaching practice and develop their skills in a supportive environment. This approach encourages autonomy, creativity, and confidence among student teachers, while also ensuring they receive necessary guidance and support from their mentor.

"Okay for me I let them perform their duty and their own ways and then their own ability but with my guidance, tagaan nako silag freedom to perform, to do whatever they want to do, especially in the classroom management and in teaching learning." (IDI. 14)

(For me, I let them perform their duties in their own ways and according to their own abilities, but with my guidance. I give them the freedom to perform, to do whatever they want to do, especially in classroom management and teaching and learning.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights that seasoned cooperating teachers can share in mentoring pre-service teachers?

Research Question No. 3 focuses on gathering insights from seasoned cooperating teachers regarding their experiences and knowledge

in mentoring pre-service teachers. The aim is to understand the valuable perspectives, strategies, and wisdom that these experienced educators have gained over time while working with pre-service teachers. The question seeks to explore various aspects of mentoring, including the challenges encountered, effective approaches utilized, and valuable lessons learned.

By examining the insights shared by seasoned cooperating teachers, the research aims to uncover best practices, practical advice, and unique perspectives that can enhance the effectiveness of mentoring programs for pre-service teachers. Overall, the focus of this question is to tap into the expertise of seasoned educators to provide valuable guidance and support for the professional development of pre-service teachers. From the answer of the participants,⁴ themes emerged inspire passion and commitment to the teaching profession, encourage continuous learning and personal development in teaching, consistently uphold diligence and dedication in teaching and be a role model.

Table 4. Insights of Seasoned Cooperating Teacher in Mentoring Student-Teacher

<i>Emerging themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statement</i>
Inspire Passion and Commitment to the Teaching Profession	"You are committed to your work, your outcome is really good. You would not say, 'oh, the principal isn't here, oh our heads aren't here, I can relax.' No, because your clients are the children and your student teacher. That is why your insights over time, I really like your attitude, you're committed." (IDI-06) "You really love teaching, you should be committed - like you're just working because it's for something, different from there are teachers like that - those who don't love teaching but have no choice because it's their destiny - you can really see that in your performance in the classrooms." (IDI-13) "As a seasoned cooperating teacher, can you say that teaching is your passion? So, your Student Teacher should also get that because if you do not have passion, you won't like it, you'll give up right away, it's really boring." (IDI-01) "You should really have a passion for teaching, even if you're really annoyed with everything because you'll pity the child so go on, just continue. So, you should be committed whether you like it or not, you will not enter that, because in reality, you'll apply for the salary, yes of course! Who applies just to chill, you really apply for money, for food, but whatever job, commitment is really needed." (IDI-04)
Encourage Continuous Learning and Personal Development in Teaching	"Keep on learning, apply what is taught. If there are difficulties, do not be ashamed to ask questions. We have a lot of resources now, you can easily find them on the internet if you're resourceful." (IDI-12) "Never stop learning, continue studying to improve your teaching skills. If you think you can do it, then pursue it and do not settle for less." (IDI-08) "You should not just stop, you should develop and innovate yourself, educate yourself. You should adapt to new learnings. There are plenty on YouTube and the internet no matter where you are." (IDI-05) "Learning never ends, so every day is a learning day. Do not give up when it's difficult. Just put in your mind that every day is a learning day. Even in your simple communication with a child, you can learn from them." (IDI-01)
Consistently Uphold Diligence and Dedication in Teaching	"Do not say 'later', do not just leave it for later. Avoid the 'manyana' system habit. I advise my Student Teacher not to do that, especially if we are in a service-oriented field. Don't rely on the 'manyana' system." (IDI-07) "So, you should really focus on your role, the real purpose of why you are here. Do not just follow the 'I'll just do this' mindset. Follow your focus, have a good attitude towards your work, and as a cooperating teacher, be serious. It is your job as a cooperating teacher. Do your part, just like both of them. I will do my part as the CT, you do your part as the ST." (IDI-03) "Study and work hard, most importantly, pray. That is the best thing to do. If there are problems, it is normal. Never give up. Think about it, you exist among millions of sperm cells in your mother's womb, and you are the one who came out, so you are the winner. So why would you quit? Survive." (IDI-02) "Work hard because in teaching, you have to work hard. Sleep less, work more. There is no resting in your work. If you cannot finish it at night, you have to finish it until dawn." (IDI-06)
Be a Role Model	"So as a cooperating teacher, you really have a significant role in helping student teachers pursue their career. You're one of their models and you encourage them to pursue whatever they envision as teachers." (IDI-09) "You cannot give what you do not have, that's the real thing, and it is not really my style to ask for output without having an input. It's like asking for input before I ask for output, like she should work on it first before asking for it." (IDI-03) "Be a role model for your student teacher, for example, in terms of dressing as a teacher, attitude; as a cooperating teacher, you shouldn't show laziness to them. You should be the role model, especially in terms of time. As a cooperating teacher, you should lead by example because you are the one they trust, so they will follow you." (IDI-10)

Inspire Passion and Commitment to the teaching profession

The theme revolves around igniting enthusiasm and dedication among educators, both experienced and novice, to ensure they are fully engaged and motivated in their roles.

The insights provided by seasoned cooperating teachers in mentoring play a crucial role in this process. These experienced educators offer invaluable guidance, sharing their passion for teaching and commitment to the profession with their mentees. Through mentorship, they impart not only pedagogical knowledge but also instill a sense of purpose and enthusiasm for teaching. They demonstrate the rewards and fulfillment that come from making a positive impact on students' lives, fostering a deep-seated dedication to the profession.

By sharing their own experiences, challenges, and triumphs, cooperating teachers inspire aspiring educators to persevere, grow, and ultimately thrive in their teaching careers.

Mrs. Eye Glass, (pseudonym) statement emphasizes the unwavering commitment and dedication required in the teaching profession. She highlights the importance of maintaining high standards and professionalism regardless of external circumstances, such as the absence of school leadership. Her focus is on prioritizing the needs of students and student teachers above all else, recognizing them as the primary clients and beneficiaries of the educational process. Mrs. Eye Glass underscores the responsibility of educators to remain steadfast in their dedication to their work, ensuring that every interaction and effort contributes positively to the growth and development of students and aspiring teachers. Her insights emphasize the significance of maintaining a strong work ethic and sense of purpose, even in the absence of immediate supervision or oversight. Ultimately, her attitude reflects a deep commitment to the teaching profession and a passion for fostering learning and mentorship.

“Committed ka sa imohang work, gwapo jud ang imohang outcome, dili jud ka moingun na ay, wala si principal, ay wala among mga head relax lang ko dili because ang imohang client are the children and your student teacher. Mao nag imohang insights nagkadugay ko gustu jud nako ang attitude, committed ka.” (IDI-06)

(You are committed to your work, your outcome is really good. You would not say, 'oh, the principal isn't here, oh our heads aren't here, I can relax.' No, because your clients are the children and your student teacher. That is why your insights over time, I really like your attitude, you are committed.)

Similarly to Mrs. Diligent (pseudonym) statement suggests a deep understanding of the varying motivations and commitments of teachers. She highlights the distinction between teachers who are genuinely passionate about teaching and those who may feel obligated to teach due to external circumstances, such as limited career options. Mrs. Diligent emphasizes the importance of passion and dedication in teaching, indicating that genuine love for the profession translates into better performance in the classroom. Her focus lies on recognizing and valuing the intrinsic motivation that drives some teachers, contrasting it with those who may lack such passion but fulfill their duties nonetheless.

“Love gyud nimo ang teaching committed gyud ka dapat-parehas sa nag trabaho lang ka kay para lang sa kuan, lahi sa naa man guy teacher nga ingun ana- kanang dili nila love ang teaching peru wala syay choice kay mao ang iyahang destiny-makita gud pod na sa imong performance sa classrooms.” (IDI-13)

(You really love teaching, you should be committed - like you are just working because it is for something, different from there are teachers like that - those who do not love teaching but have no choice because it is their destiny - you can really see that in your performance in the classrooms.)

In addition, with Mrs. Red, (pseudonym) statement underscores the importance of passion in teaching and its impact on both the mentor and the student teacher. She implies that teaching requires a genuine passion to endure its challenges and complexities. By stating that teaching without passion can lead to boredom and a quick abandonment of the profession, Mrs. Red emphasizes the significance of passion as a driving force for sustained commitment and fulfillment in teaching. Her focus lies in instilling this understanding in both seasoned teachers, like herself, and student teachers, highlighting its critical role in shaping their experiences and longevity in the field.

“As a seasoned cooperating teacher maka ana ka ba nga passion nimo ang teaching ba, so, dapat makuha pod na sa imong ST nimo kay kung wala man gud kay pashion dili ka ganahan mo give-up gyud dayun ka, laay kaayu.” (IDI-01)

(As a seasoned cooperating teacher, you can say that teaching is your passion. So, your Student Teacher should also get that because if you do not have passion, you will not like it, you will give up right away, it is really boring.)

Moreover Mrs. Casual, (pseudonym) statement highlights the necessity of commitment in teaching, even when facing challenges or feeling annoyed. She emphasizes that while having a passion for teaching is important, commitment is equally crucial, especially during difficult times. Mrs. Casual suggests that teachers should persevere and continue teaching, even when they feel frustrated or disheartened, because their commitment ultimately serves the well-being of their students.

By acknowledging the practical aspect of needing a job for financial stability, she stresses the importance of maintaining dedication and professionalism in fulfilling one's duties as a teacher. Her focus lies in instilling a sense of responsibility and perseverance in both seasoned teachers and student teachers, emphasizing the importance of commitment in the teaching profession.

“Dapat naa gyd pod kay pashion for teaching, maskin paglagot na kayka sa nga tanan kay malooy man lagi ka sa bata so hala padayun gihapon... So dapat committed jud mo whether you like it or not di man gyud ka mosulod ana, kay kita in reality, mosulod mangaply man gyud kag para sa sweldo kwarta, para naa naay ikapakaon, peru dapat kay maskig unsa man nga trabaho kay kinahanglan man jud gud ang commitment.” (IDI-04)

(You should really have a passion for teaching, even if you are really annoyed with everything because you'll pity the child, so go on, just continue. So, you should be committed whether you like it or not, you won't enter that, because in reality, you'll apply for the salary, yes of course! Who applies just to chill, you really apply for money, for food, but whatever job, commitment is really needed.)

Encourage Continuous Learning and Personal Development in Teaching

The focus of encouraging continuous learning and personal development in teaching is to foster a culture of growth and improvement among educators. This theme emphasizes the importance of ongoing professional development, reflection, and refinement of teaching practices. From the perspective of a seasoned cooperating teacher in mentoring, this theme involves guiding and supporting new teachers in their journey towards becoming effective educators.

It entails providing opportunities for them to engage in reflective practices, seek feedback, and continuously refine their teaching techniques. Seasoned teachers can share their own experiences, insights, and resources to inspire and support the professional growth of their mentees. By prioritizing continuous learning and personal development, both mentors and mentees can enhance their teaching skills, stay updated with the latest educational trends and research, and ultimately provide better learning experiences for their students.

The statement by Mrs. On Time, (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of continuous learning, practical application of knowledge, and seeking help when faced with difficulties. She encourages individuals not to feel ashamed to ask questions, as there are abundant resources available, especially on the internet, for those who are resourceful. In the context of mentoring, this advice suggests that mentors should support and guide their mentees in acquiring knowledge, applying it in real-life situations, and seeking assistance when needed, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and learning.

“Keep on learning, kung unsay itudlo e apply lang jud unsa more on kuan jud, kung naay mga lisodan di jud maolaw mangutana unya daghan man tag resources karon kaya ra kaayu sa internet oy kung resourceful lang jud ka nga pag katao.” (IDI-12)

(Keep on learning, apply what is taught. If there are difficulties, do not be ashamed to ask questions. We have a lot of resources now, you can easily find them on the internet if you are resourceful.)

Similarly with Mrs. Happy, (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of lifelong learning for teachers, highlighting that continual study and improvement are essential for enhancing teaching skills. By encouraging educators to persistently seek opportunities for professional development, she fosters a culture of growth and excellence within the teaching community. Moreover, her advice to pursue goals without settling for less underscores the importance of ambition and determination in achieving success in the field of education. As a mentor, Mrs. Happy likely believes in guiding and supporting teachers in their journey towards continual improvement and excellence in teaching.

“Never stop learning, padayun sa pag toon para ma improve pa jud ang pagiging teacher then if you think mahimo nimo ni, if you think you can do it, then pursue then do not settle for less.” (IDI-08)

(Never stop learning, continue studying to improve your teaching skills. If you think you can do it, then pursue it and do not settle for less.)

In addition with Mrs. Short Hair, (pseudonym) her statement reflects her belief in the importance of continuous self-development and innovation in the field of education. As a seasoned cooperating teacher and mentor, she understands the value of staying updated with new learning techniques and methodologies. By encouraging educators to adapt to new knowledge and skills, she fosters a mindset of growth and adaptability. Mrs. Short Hair likely emphasizes leveraging resources like YouTube and the internet to access a wide range of educational content, regardless of geographical location. Through her insights, she aims to empower teachers to embrace lifelong learning and proactively seek opportunities for self-improvement, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness in the classroom and as mentors to others.

“Dili ka dapat mag pundo lang sa imong-e develop jud imong kaugalingon nya innovate imong kaugalingon, e educate imong kaugalingon, dapat mag-adapt kag new learning daghan sa youtube gihapon sa internet baskin asa ka.” (IDI-05)

(You should not just stop, you should develop and innovate yourself, educate yourself. You should adapt to new learnings. There are plenty on YouTube and the internet no matter where you are.)

Moreover Mrs. Red (pseudonym) statement embodies the philosophy of continuous learning and resilience in the face of challenges. As a seasoned cooperating teacher and mentor, she recognizes that learning is a lifelong process that extends beyond the confines of formal education. By emphasizing that every day presents opportunities for learning, she encourages educators to adopt a growth mindset and approach each day with curiosity and openness to new experiences. Mrs. Red highlights the importance of persevering through difficulties, reminding teachers not to give up but to view obstacles as opportunities for growth and learning.

“Learning never ends, so everyday is a learning days so dili ka mo give up na kanang lisod mani sya oy di nako kaya no,so, imo lang gyung ibutang sa imong mind nga everyday is a learning day, may sa bisan baya ug sa simple lang nimo nga pag communicate sa bata naa kay mabal-an sa ilaha.” (IDI-01)

(Learning never ends, so every day is a learning day. Do not give up when it is difficult. Just put in your mind that every day is a learning day. Even in your simple communication with a child, you can learn from them.)

Additionally, her mention of learning from simple interactions with children underscores the idea that valuable insights can be gained from everyday experiences, further emphasizing the importance of humility and openness to learning from others, regardless of age or

background. Overall, Mrs. Red's insights serve to inspire and motivate educators to embrace a lifelong journey of learning and personal growth, both in their professional practice and in their interactions with others.

Consistently Uphold Diligence and Dedication in teaching

The theme related to the insights of a seasoned cooperating teacher in mentoring is the importance of diligence and dedication in teaching. This theme emphasizes the commitment and perseverance required to excel in the field of education, particularly in the role of mentoring aspiring teachers. Seasoned cooperating teachers understand the significance of consistently upholding high standards of diligence and dedication, both in their own teaching practice and in guiding and supporting the development of new educators.

They recognize that effective mentoring requires not only sharing knowledge and expertise but also demonstrating a strong work ethic and a passion for teaching. By embodying these qualities, seasoned cooperating teachers inspire and motivate mentees to strive for excellence and to approach their teaching with the same level of dedication and commitment. Overall, the theme underscores the importance of diligence and dedication as essential pillars of effective mentoring in the field of education.

Mrs. Chocolate, (pseudonym) statement emphasizes the importance of proactivity and avoiding procrastination, particularly in the context of mentoring within service-oriented fields. By advising her Student Teacher not to adopt the "manyana" system, she is encouraging a mindset of urgency and responsibility. Mrs. Chocolate likely believes that in service-oriented professions, such as teaching, delaying tasks or leaving them for later can have detrimental effects on student learning and overall effectiveness in the role. She likely stresses the need for prompt action and follow-through in fulfilling responsibilities and commitments to students and colleagues.

"Do not say unya nalang, dili lang sa ko ana, manyana system habit, akong e advice lanca akong ST nga dili gyud ana, labina kung naa nata sa service, dili gyud ka mag kuan, nga manyana systems magsalig lang ka." (IDI-07)

(Do not say 'later', do not just leave it for later. Avoid the 'manyana' system habit. I advise my Student Teacher not to do that, especially if we are in a service-oriented field. Do not rely on the 'manyana' system.)

Additionally, her advice may reflect the importance of time management and prioritization in effectively balancing the demands of teaching and mentoring. Overall, Mrs. Chocolate's insights underscore the importance of taking initiative and avoiding the habit of postponing tasks, particularly in professions where timely action is essential for success.

Similarly with Mrs. Leader, (pseudonym) her statement reflects her deep commitment to the mentoring process and the importance of clarity of purpose and dedication in the role of a seasoned cooperating teacher. She underscores the seriousness of the mentoring relationship by emphasizing the need to focus on the real purpose of being a cooperating teacher and avoiding a mindset of casualness or indifference. Mrs. Leader likely believes that a positive attitude and a strong work ethic are essential for effective mentoring, as they contribute to creating a conducive learning environment for student teachers. She emphasizes the importance of both parties fulfilling their respective roles and responsibilities, with the cooperating teacher providing guidance and support while the student teacher actively engages in the learning process.

"So, mag fucos man jud ka sa unsa imong role, real purpose nganung naa ka diria mo kalat naman gud na mo follow naman gud ng "tarbaho ko ni" imo mang gisunod sa imohang fucos pod, attitude towards sa imong-ano ba dili ka magbinuklakbol ka, and the part pod sa cooperating teacher be serious, trabahoa imohang trabaho as the cooperating teacher. Do your part pareho silang duha, do your part, I will do my part as the CT, do your part as the ST." (IDI-03)

(So, you should really focus on your role, the real purpose of why you are here. Do not just follow the 'I will just do this' mindset. Always focus, have a good attitude towards your work, and as a cooperating teacher, be serious. It is your job as a cooperating teacher. Do your part, just like both of them. I will do my part as the CT, you do your part as the ST.)

Additionally, Mrs. Leader's statement highlights the collaborative nature of the mentoring relationship, with both parties expected to contribute to its success. Overall, her insights underscore the importance of professionalism, commitment, and mutual respect in the mentorship dynamic, aiming to cultivate a culture of excellence and growth within the teaching profession.

In addition with Mrs. Home, (pseudonym) her statement reflects a holistic approach to mentoring, combining the importance of academic diligence with spiritual guidance and resilience. As a seasoned cooperating teacher, she emphasizes the value of studying and working hard to achieve success, recognizing the importance of dedication and effort in the teaching profession. Additionally, Mrs. Home underscores the power of prayer as a source of strength and guidance in facing challenges, highlighting the role of faith in overcoming obstacles. She mentions of encountering problems as a normal part of life serves to normalize setbacks and encourage perseverance in the face of adversity. By reminding her mentees of their unique journey into existence, she instills a sense of resilience and determination, emphasizing the value of every individual's life and the potential for greatness within them.

"Study and study work hard most of all pray, that's the best thing to do, then if their are mga problem normal ranjud na never give-up kung бага me exist naka among millions of sperm cells didto sa tagoangkan sa imong inahan sa imong kuan ikaw ang nigawas sonikaw and nanalo, so you are the winner, so why you quit? Survive." (IDI 02)

(Study and work hard, most importantly, pray. That's the best thing to do. If there are problems, it's normal. Never give up. Think about it, you exist among millions of sperm cells in your mother's womb, and you are the one who came out, so you are the winner. So why would you quit? Survive.)

Overall, Mrs. Home's insights suggest a compassionate and nurturing approach to mentoring, one that values both academic and personal development, resilience, and faith. She seeks to inspire her mentees to embrace challenges, never give up, and strive for success with a steadfast belief in their own abilities.

Mrs. Eye Glass's statement underscores the demanding nature of the teaching profession and the necessity for dedication and hard work, reflecting her insights as a seasoned cooperating teacher in mentoring. She emphasizes the importance of putting in extra effort and sacrificing personal time, including sleep, in order to fulfill the responsibilities and commitments associated with teaching. As a mentor, Mrs. Eye Glass likely believes in instilling a strong work ethic in her mentees, preparing them for the rigorous demands of the profession. Her advice to work hard and prioritize completing tasks, even if it means sacrificing sleep, suggests a commitment to excellence and a sense of urgency in meeting professional obligations.

"Work hard because in teaching you have to work hard, sleep less, work more walay pahulaybkay imong work dili mahuman di dalahon gyud nimos balay so pagka dili nimo mahuman sa gabii humanon nimog kadlawon." (IDI-06)

(Work hard because in teaching, you have to work hard. Sleep less, work more. There is no resting in your work. If you cannot finish it at night, you have to finish it until dawn.)

Furthermore, Mrs. Eye Glass's statement may also reflect the reality of time constraints and workload in teaching, where educators often find themselves with extensive responsibilities that extend beyond regular working hours. By encouraging her mentees to persevere and push through fatigue to complete their work, she reinforces the notion that success in teaching requires sustained effort and diligence. Overall, Mrs. Eye Glass's insights serve to motivate and prepare her mentees for the challenges they will encounter in their teaching careers, emphasizing the importance of hard work, resilience, and a willingness to go the extra mile in pursuit of excellence.

Be a Role Model

The theme of "Be a Role Model" in mentoring highlights the importance of seasoned cooperating teachers serving as exemplars for their mentees. They understand that their actions, attitudes, and behaviors directly influence the development of their mentees. By consistently demonstrating professionalism, expertise, empathy, and a commitment to continuous learning, they inspire and guide their mentees to become effective educators themselves. This theme emphasizes the idea that effective mentoring goes beyond just imparting knowledge; it involves modeling the values and practices that contribute to success in the teaching profession.

Mrs. Vowel2, (pseudonym) statement underscores the crucial role of seasoned cooperating teachers in shaping the professional journey of student teachers. She acknowledges that as a cooperating teacher, one serves as a model for aspiring educators, influencing their growth and development. Mrs. Vowel2 emphasizes the importance of fostering an environment where student teachers feel empowered to pursue their unique visions for their teaching careers. By providing guidance, support, and encouragement, cooperating teachers like Mrs. Vowel2 play a vital role in helping mentees realize their potential and navigate the challenges of the teaching profession. Overall, her insight highlights the responsibility and privilege that comes with mentoring student teachers and shaping the future of education.

"So as cooperating teacher naa jud kay dako nga role nga to help student teacher to pursue their career, isa jud ka sa mga model nila isa jud ka sa mo encourage sa ilaha nga mo pursue kung unsa man ilahang as a teacher..." (IDI-09)

(So as a cooperating teacher, you really have a significant role in helping student teachers pursue their career. You are one of their models and you encourage them to pursue whatever they envision as teachers.)

In addition with Mrs. Leader, (pseudonym) insights emphasize the importance of personal development and preparation before expecting others to follow as a mentor. She believes that mentors must embody the qualities they wish to instill in their mentees. By stating, "You can't give what you don't have," Mrs. Leader suggests that mentors must first cultivate the skills, knowledge, and attributes they seek to impart to their mentees. Additionally, she highlights the importance of leading by example, indicating that mentors should demonstrate the behaviors and attitudes they expect from their mentees. Overall, Mrs. Leader's insights stress the necessity of self-reflection, growth, and readiness as foundational elements of effective mentoring and being a role model in the process.

"You cannot give what you do not have, that is the real thing and then it's not really my.. kind nga I ask for a inputs without... I ask for an output without having an input. Kumbaga ba mohatag sa ko mo input sa ko bago nako sya pangayuan ug output, kumbaga trabahoe sa sya una sya pangayue." (IDI-03)

(You cannot give what you do not have, that is the real thing, and it is not really my style to ask for output without having an input. It is like asking for input before I ask for output, like she should work on it first before asking for it.)

Moreover Mrs. Fresh, (pseudonym) insights emphasize the importance of setting a positive example for student teachers in various aspects of professional conduct. She highlights the significance of dressing appropriately and maintaining a professional attitude as

essential components of being a role model. Mrs. Fresh also stresses the importance of demonstrating diligence and punctuality, as well as avoiding laziness, to inspire mentees to adopt similar work ethics. Additionally, she underscores the role of trust in the mentor-mentee relationship, emphasizing that cooperating teachers should lead by example since they are the primary source of guidance and support for student teachers. Overall, Mrs. Fresh insights highlight the multifaceted nature of being a role model in mentoring, encompassing not only professional demeanor but also work ethic and reliability.

"Be a role model sa imohang ST, example in terms of pananamit as a teacher, attitude ikaw na cooperating teacher dili nimo ipakita sa iyaha nga tapulan ka dapat ikaw jud ang role model ana ug sa labaw na sa time ikaw cooperating teacher ikaw jud ang mag ana di sad ka magpalate kay ikaw man ang role model, ikaw ang gi in trust sa iyaha so sundon gyud ka niya." (IDI-10)

(Be a role model for your student teacher, for example, in terms of dressing as a teacher, attitude; as a cooperating teacher, you should not show laziness to them. You should be the role model, especially in terms of time. As a cooperating teacher, you should lead by example because you are the one they trust, so they will follow you.)

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study has shed light on the experiences and practices of seasoned cooperating teachers in mentoring pre-service teachers within public elementary schools. Through thematic analysis, key insights have emerged regarding the strategies, challenges, and benefits associated with mentorship in teacher education.

As I reflect on my research journey, I am struck by the dedication and commitment demonstrated by seasoned mentors in guiding the next generation of educators. Their unwavering support, coupled with their passion for teaching, has been instrumental in shaping the professional identities and practices of pre-service teachers.

Moreover, this study underscores the importance of effective mentorship in teacher education and highlights the significant role that seasoned cooperating teachers play in supporting the growth and development of future educators. It is imperative that we continue to prioritize mentorship in teacher preparation programs, providing resources, support, and professional development opportunities for seasoned mentors to enhance their mentoring practices. By doing so, we can ensure that pre-service teachers receive the guidance and support they need to thrive in the classroom and make a positive impact on student learning.

As I conclude this research journey, I am inspired by the potential for mentorship to transform teacher education and contribute to the ongoing improvement of educational systems worldwide.

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